

THE ROLE OF USING MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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As we know that, schools have relied heavily on extrinsically motivated manners. Statistics says that in most countries that teach foreign language, school level rule does not emphasize the function of foreign language as a tool for communication but instead focuses on skills of grammatical forms and structures that are often assessed on examination lists. Therefore, students work very hard to try to pass these exams in order to please tutors and parents rather than develop an internal thirst for knowledge and experience for this field. It is fact that students often lose interest in foreign language learning as a result. After some years of study few foreign language learners are competent to communicate freely with native speakers. Even teachers to provide students with authentic, functional, interactive, and constructive language learning environments to reduce student's motivation for their knowledge.

Some pedagogical techniques that can help accomplish the ultimate purpose of communicative language teaching of foreign languages. Scientist Brown says that the utilization of technology such as different mp3, videos, and IT technologies. Multimedia is an instructional approach that integrates computer assisted instruction and multimedia which can help students develop the various competencies mobilized in communication from foreign languages.

These kind of studies effects of level of learners intrinsic motivation and use of embedded motivational strategies with an enhanced relevance component in a computer for foreign language learning (English). There are two main dependent variables, learners achievement and learners perception of motivation. Well, were examined as well as the interaction between these two factors in learning foreign language learning. Behavioristic Foreign Language Teaching by Computer (B-FLTbyC), Communicative Foreign Language Teaching by Computer and Integrative Foreign Language Teaching by Computer. Each group fits into a certain level of technological as well as a certain pedagogical approach.

The first group, Behavioristic was created in the 1950s and implemented during the 1960s and 1970s. It can be counted as a sub-component of the broader field of computer technology assisted instruction. Notified by the behavioristic learning model, this model of features repetitive language drills and this way of teaching is particularly popular in the United States of America. They thought that the computer was viewed as a mechanical teacher which never grew tired or assessment and allowed students to work at an individual tempo. Finally behavioristic gravitated to the personal computer. This was first designed and implemented in the epoch of the mainframe of technological evolution.

The second group, Communicative was created between the 1970s and 1980s. During these years, behavioristic approaches to language teaching were being rejected at both the

theoretical and pedagogical level and later new personal computers were creating larger possibilities for individual learning. Supporters of Communicative stressed that computer-based activities should focus more on the usage of forms than on the forms themselves. Teaching grammar implicitly rather than explicitly, allows and encourages students to generate original utterances rather than just manipulate prefabricated language and use the target language predominantly or even exclusively.

The Communicative group corresponded to cognitive theories which stressed that learning was a process of discovery, expression, and development. Famous software developed in this period included text reconstruction programs (which permitted students working alone or in groups to rearrange words and texts to discover patterns of foreign language and meaning) and simulations. Supporters of Communicative, believed that the attention was not so much on what the learners did with the technology but rather on how they interacted with each other while working with the computer technologies.

While Communicative was seen as an advance over Behavioristic, this too came under the lens of criticism. In the end of the 1980s and in the beginning of the 1990s, critics stated that the computer technologies were still being used in an ad hoc and disconnected fashion and thus found itself making a greater contribution to marginal rather than central elements of the language learning process. This fitted to a broader reassessment of communicative foreign language teaching theory and practice. However, in the third group it can be observed that the task-based, project-based, and content-based approaches, all sought to integrate students in authentic environments and also to integrate the various skills of foreign language learning. It opened a new perspective on computer technology and foreign language learning, which has been termed Integrative, a perspective which seeks both to integrate various skills (for example, listening, speaking, reading, and writing) and also integrate technology more holistically into the foreign language learning process. In the third approach, learners learn to use a variety of computer based technological tools as an ongoing process of foreign language learning and usage, rather than visiting the computer laboratory on a once-a-week basis for isolated topics.

Pedagogical staff should realize that every technique in language classrooms can be enhanced by an effective strategy of language which does not need to be outstanding or inspirational in foreign language learning by informational technologies. Without stopping classroom practice can be very motivating through teachers' careful design of informational technologies. A few things with native language that inspires students' thinking about personal goals when checking homework and other exercises, all tasks with feedbacks, cooperative works, or a interesting things that can stimulate problem solving can increase students' motivation in foreign language learning by informational technologies.

In conclusion, the multimedia networked computers possess a varied set of informational, communicative and publishing tools, which are now potentially at the fingertips of every learner. It provides not only the possibilities for a much higher integrated use of computer technology, but also the imperative for such a use, such as learning to read, write, and communicate through computer technology, which has become an essential feature of our modern life.

The combination of informational technologies especially into classrooms had a positive effect on learning outcomes in this study of learning. It is very important that pedagogical staffs who is learning English as a second language take the first step to integrate technology into classroom instruction and also the same time they try to use informational technologies.

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